

GaAs-based photonic integrated circuit platform enabling monolithic ring-resonator-coupled lasers

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(Dated: 27 August 2024)

This paper reports on a monolithically integrated gallium arsenide (GaAs)-based photonic integrated circuit platform for wavelengths around 1064 nm. Enabled by spatially selective quantum well removal and two-step epitaxial growth, it supports on-chip gain as well as passive waveguides. In addition, shallow- and deep-etched waveguides are realized. The former result in waveguide losses of less than 2 dB/cm, while the latter enable compact integrated waveguide components. To demonstrate the performance of the platform, racetrack ring resonators based on deep-etched Euler bends and shallow-etched directional couplers are realized, achieving high intrinsic quality factors of $2.6 \cdot 10^5$ for TE and $3.2 \cdot 10^5$ for TM modes. To demonstrate the use of these resonators, ring-resonator-coupled lasers are fabricated, resulting in one-sided output powers of up to 14 mW and single-mode operation with 40 dB side-mode suppression. The successful integration of ring resonators on a GaAs-based active/passive photonic integrated circuit platform paves the way for the realization of fully monolithic, widely tunable, and narrow linewidth ring-resonator-coupled laser sources.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gallium arsenide (GaAs)-based diode lasers can provide direct light emission in the wavelength range from 630 nm to 1180 nm.^{1–3} This spectral region is relevant for various applications, including spectroscopy^{4,5}, quantum photonics^{6,7}, and bio-sensing/imaging⁸. Most of the aforementioned applications require tailored sources beyond standard Fabry-Pérot type lasers to achieve narrow linewidths⁹, multiple wavelengths¹⁰ or tunable wavelength emission^{11,12}. However, meeting these demands necessitates the integration of one or more additional waveguide components, such as wavelength-selective elements of the distributed feedback (DFB)^{13,14} or distributed Bragg reflector (DBR)^{15,16} type, compact waveguide bends^{17,18}, couplers^{10,19}, and thermo- or electro-optic phase shifters^{17,19,20}.

Although all of these components have already been realized in different GaAs-based devices separately (cf. Refs. 10, 13–20) there is no established GaAs photonic integrated circuit (PIC) platform which can provide optical gain, passive waveguides as well as the aforementioned functionalities on a single chip. Additionally, most GaAs-based waveguide components have not yet reached the level of maturity seen in InP PICs, where a well-established foundry ecosystem exists.^{21–23} The difference in maturity between GaAs- and InP-based PIC technologies has both economic and technical reasons. The economic reason is due to the high demand for telecom-related applications that require light emission in the O-band (around 1310 nm) and C-band (around 1550 nm). The technological reason is the more complicated multi-step epitaxy process for the GaAs/AlGaAs material sys-

tem, which is highly susceptible to oxygen at the regrowth interface and has a high growth velocity of crystalline defects. However, significant progress has been made in recent years to advance and mature the two-step epitaxial growth of GaAs-based lasers.^{9,12,24} This progress includes devices emitting not only around 1 μ m but also at a wavelength of 778 nm.²⁵

Based on this progress, this work presents a GaAs-based PIC platform that integrates active gain sections emitting around 1050 nm and passive waveguides through two-step epitaxy. In addition, the platform features both shallow- and deep-etched waveguides on the same chip. Figure 1 shows the resulting waveguide cross sections and mentions their potential use cases. The most notable difference to standard GaAs lasers is the now available high lateral (in-plane) index contrast and the resulting high modal confinement of the deep-etched waveguides, which is essential for the realization of compact integrated waveguide components. Building on this, we demonstrate a high quality racetrack ring resonator together with several other integrated waveguide components such as semiconductor optical amplifiers (SOA) providing optical gain, low-loss passive waveguide routing, spot-size converters and couplers, all monolithically integrated. To demonstrate the use of these waveguide components, ring-resonator-coupled lasers are fabricated and characterized.

In the context of PIC-based lasers, high-quality ring resonators can provide frequency-selective feedback to stabilize and tune the emitted radiation, resulting in narrow linewidth and widely tunable lasers.²⁶ At emission wavelengths around 1050 nm, these lasers are of interest for applications like optical coherence tomography (OCT)⁸ as well as airborne and space-based light detection and ranging (LIDAR) systems¹².

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II. DESIGN AND CONCEPT

In this section, we provide a detailed explanation and introduction to the design and concept of our GaAs-based PIC platform, which features a newly developed vertical structure, various waveguide types, and different integrated waveguide components.

A. Waveguide design

The introduced PIC platform utilizes four different types of waveguides, as shown schematically in Fig. 1. From left to right, these are a shallow-etched waveguide with an active region used in sections where optical gain is required, a shallow-etched and low-loss waveguide without an active region for low-loss waveguide routing, and a deep-etched waveguide with and without an active region. These deep-etched waveguides provide high in-plane optical confinement, which is essential for compact waveguide bends.

The shallow-etched waveguides are designed to support only the fundamental waveguide mode. This is achieved by combining a $2.5\ \mu\text{m}$ wide ridge with an effective index step Δn_{eff} of $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ which is obtained by etching index guiding trenches from the p-side down to a residual layer thickness above the active region of $d_{\text{res},s} = 0.3\ \mu\text{m}$, see Fig. 2 (a). The corresponding waveguide cross section including information on the refractive index distribution and the fundamental TE mode intensity is shown in Fig. 2 (c).

In contrast, the deep-etched waveguides are designed to be $2.0\ \mu\text{m}$ wide and are etched through the complete vertical waveguide into the AlGaAs n-cladding layer, resulting in $d_{\text{res}} = -0.8\ \mu\text{m}$. The corresponding waveguide,

FIG. 1. Schematic illustration of the different waveguide cross sections of the presented GaAs-PIC platform. Possible use cases are listed below each waveguide type. Note that the waveguide dimensions are not to scale.

FIG. 2. Waveguide design of the presented GaAs-PIC platform. (a) shows the vertical waveguide design, where the black and red lines represent the refractive index profile and the free carrier losses caused by the doping profile. The resulting profiles of the fundamental waveguide modes, and the corresponding modal indices are shown in (b). Here, the index profiles are drawn as gray lines. In both panels solid and dashed lines represent the active and passive waveguides, respectively. The bottom two images show the refractive index cross section of a (c) $2.5\ \mu\text{m}$ wide shallow-etched active waveguide and a (d) $2.0\ \mu\text{m}$ wide deep-etched passive waveguide. The red contour lines depict the corresponding fundamental mode intensity profiles.

as shown in Fig. 2 (d), supports the first three TE modes. However, reducing the ridge width further to limit the number of supported modes would increase the spatial overlap of the fundamental mode, with the etched ridge sidewalls potentially increasing scattering losses. Therefore, it is essential that all deep-etched waveguide components are designed to avoid modal cross coupling.^{27,28}

The waveguide types introduced above are based on a vertical structure that was designed to minimize losses, provide strong vertical optical confinement, and reduce parasitic reflections at the active/passive interface. The structure is based on a $596\ \text{nm}$ thick undoped GaAs waveguide core that embeds a $\text{Ga}_{0.52}\text{In}_{0.48}\text{P}$ etchstop layer placed directly beneath an $\text{In}_{0.28}\text{Ga}_{0.72}\text{As}/\text{GaAs}$ double quantum well using $\text{GaAs}_{0.85}\text{P}_{0.15}$ spacer layers similar to the structure realized in Ref. 9. However, unlike in the cited work, both the n- and p-cladding layers were designed to offer a large index step of $\Delta n_n = 0.15$ and $\Delta n_p = 0.23$ by using $\text{Al}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{As}$ with $x = 0.25$

and $x = 0.40$ having layer thicknesses of 2030 nm and 1030 nm, respectively. On the p-side, a 330 nm thick $\text{Al}_{0.2}\text{Ga}_{0.8}\text{As}$ intermediate layer was added between the waveguide core and the p-cladding to increase the spatial overlap of the vertical mode with the p-side. This design reduces the dependence of the modal index on the residual layer thickness in the etched regions, which is essential to reliably fabricate the shallow-etched waveguides. The resulting profiles of the refractive index and the free carrier absorption for the chosen doping profile are shown as black and red lines in Fig. 2 (a). The corresponding profiles of the vertical fundamental mode and modal indices are shown in panel (b) as red and blue lines, respectively. In both panels results of the passive waveguide are represented by dashed lines. Here, the active region is removed between the first and second growth step which will be described in Sec. III. As a consequence of the quantum well removal, the passive waveguide is approximately 65 nm thinner compared to the active one, resulting in a slightly narrower vertical mode profile.

The active and passive vertical waveguide modal losses caused by the free-carrier absorption profile (see Fig. 2 (a)) were calculated by determining the overlap of the corresponding modes and the doping profile leading to 0.08 cm^{-1} and 0.09 cm^{-1} , respectively. These 1D results are in good agreement with the values obtained by 2D simulations for the deep-etched waveguides. The losses of the shallow-etched waveguides are slightly lower, but differ only in the third decimal place. The modal distributions and the resulting loss figures presented in this section were obtained using Photon Design FIMMWAVE (for more information see Appendix A 1). This tool was also used to obtain the simulation results presented in the following section.

B. Ring resonator design

To demonstrate the performance and versatility of our GaAs-PIC platform we realized an integrated racetrack ring resonator consisting of several waveguide components. A schematic view of the ring resonator is shown in Fig. 3 (a). Its design follows the idea to combine compact, deep-etched U-bends with straight and low loss shallow-etched waveguides combined by mode spot-size converters^{29,30}.

The U-bends are designed to avoid cross-coupling of different modes within the deep-etched waveguide by an adiabatic mode transition using Euler bends.³¹ Here the curvature $C(s)$ rises linearly from zero to its maximal value C_{max} (minimal radius R_{min}) and back to zero along the path length s following:²⁸

$$C(s) = C_{\text{max}} \left(1 - \left| \frac{2s}{s_{\text{max}}} - 1 \right| \right) \quad (1)$$

where s_{max} is the cumulated path length. The maximal curvature follows $C_{\text{max}} = R_{\text{min}}^{-1} = 2\theta/s_{\text{max}}$ with θ being

the full bend angle in units of radians. The effective radius of an Euler U-bend as defined in Fig. 3 (a) can be calculated as $R_{\text{eff}} = 0.22 \cdot s_{\text{max}}$.³¹ Figure 3 (b) shows the simulated mode transmittance $T_{\{m,m\}}$ of the first three TE modes $m = \{1, 2, 3\}$ as function of R_{eff} for a U-bend formed by the passive and deep-etched waveguide introduced before. The fundamental mode shows a high transmittance of $T_{\{1,1\}} > 0.99$ for $75 \mu\text{m} < R_{\text{eff}} < 150 \mu\text{m}$. In addition, the modal cross-coupling between the first three modes is smaller than -30 dB for $R_{\text{eff}} > 100 \mu\text{m}$ and the reflection is below -80 dB for all investigated R_{eff} .

To connect the deep- and shallow-etched waveguides the ring resonator contains four spot-size converters which adiabatically transform the mode profile shown in (a) into that of (b) and vice versa. The used design is schematically shown on the left side of Fig. 3 (a) and is similar to those used in Refs. 27 and 32. Here, the waveguide width and the shallow-etched part next to the ridge is tapered linearly from $w_s = 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ to $w_d = 2.0 \mu\text{m}$ and from $w_t = 10 \mu\text{m}$ to $0 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The corresponding simulated fundamental mode transmittance as function of the taper length L_t is shown in Fig. 3 (c) for three different values of the residual layer thickness d_{res} . For spot-size converters longer than $80 \mu\text{m}$ and $d_{\text{res},s} = 0.3 \mu\text{m}$ the transmittance $T_{\{1,1\}}$ is larger than 99%. In addition, the coupling into higher modes $T_{\{1,m\}}$ of the deep-etched waveguide was calculated to be smaller than -20 dB .

The coupling between the ring resonator and its bus waveguides was realized by directional couplers formed by shallow-etched waveguides. A cross section of the coupler is shown on the left side of Fig. 3 (a). Results of calculated cross-over lengths obtained by performing a super-mode analysis are shown in panel (d). It is evident that a coupler gap in the order of $1 \mu\text{m}$ is sufficient to obtain a cross-over length of below 1 mm. The coupler region is formed by the straight waveguide inside the ring resonator and two cascaded sine S-bends which are each $750 \mu\text{m}$ long and cover a lateral offset of $10 \mu\text{m}$. Shallow-etched waveguides have been used to keep the critical dimensions of the coupler gap in the order of $1 \mu\text{m}$, which allows its fabrication using i-line lithography. In contrast, the strong lateral confinement of the deep-etched waveguide would have required coupler gap dimensions in the order of 100 nm. To account for unavoidable etch depth uncertainties during fabrication, a variation in the coupler gap has been realized, spanning from $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ to $2.5 \mu\text{m}$.

The ring resonators investigated in this work were based on Euler U-bends with $R_{\text{eff}} = 75 \mu\text{m}$, resulting in an individual bend length of $L_U = 341.5 \mu\text{m}$. The spot-size converter was chosen to be $L_t = 150 \mu\text{m}$ long and the straight waveguide to have a length of $892 \mu\text{m}$. This results in a total ring circumference of $L_R = 3067 \mu\text{m}$. The gap of the directional couplers used to couple the light in and out of the resonator was $w_{\text{gap}} = 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ for all measured devices.

FIG. 3. (a) Schematic depiction of the used ring resonator design. It is based on Euler U-bends, spot-size converter, and directional coupler. Selected simulation results of these waveguide components are depicted in (b)-(d) and were obtained using Photon Design FIMMWAVE/FIMMPROP (see Appendix A 1). (b) shows the transmittance of the first three TE modes through the U-bend as function of the effective radius R_{eff} . (c) gives the fundamental mode transmittance through the spot size converter as function of its length. (d) depicts the cross-over length of a uniform direction coupler formed by shallow-etched waveguides. The solid, dashed, and dotted black lines in (c) and (d) were obtained assuming a residual layer thickness of $0.2 \mu\text{m}$, $0.3 \mu\text{m}$, and $0.4 \mu\text{m}$, respectively.

III. PROCESS AND FABRICATION

The vertical waveguide structure was grown by a two-step metal organic vapor phase epitaxy (MOVPE) process, as described in Refs. 9 and 11. The first growth step concludes with the double InGaAs quantum well and a GaAs top layer. Consequently, no AlGaAs cladding layer is exposed between the growth steps which minimizes oxygen incorporation and oxidation at the regrowth interface avoiding the formation of deep level traps and defects. Next, a positive resist is coated and exposed using i-line lithography to cover the active device sections. In the remaining area, the quantum wells and the GaAs top layer are removed by a wet chemical etch step. Following the resist removal, the GaInP etch-stop layer is removed using selective wet chemistry. The second growth process is performed in the same MOVPE reactor used before and involves in-situ surface cleaning using CBr_4 , followed by the completion of the full vertical structure as outlined in Sec. II. Figure 4 (c) illustrates an active-passive interface fabricated by the process described above. It can be seen that the passive waveguide without an active region is approximately 65 nm thinner compared to the active waveguide.

After the epitaxial growth, the waveguides were defined using i-line lithography and formed by dry etching trenches into the p-side. Here, a BCl_3/Cl_2 -based reactive ion etching process was applied utilizing a parallel plate reactor (SENTECH SI 591) under a high bias voltage. The lithography and etch step has to be repeated

twice to form the shallow- and deep-etched regions separately as in Ref. 10, requiring an etch depth of 1495 nm ($d_{\text{res},s} = 0.3 \mu\text{m}$) and 2595 nm ($d_{\text{res},d} = -0.8 \mu\text{m}$), respectively. It is important to note that the shallow-etch step is more critical regarding etch depth variations than the deep one since it directly influences the resulting effective refractive index Δn_{eff} , see Fig. 3 (c) and (d). In contrast, the lateral index guiding of the deep-etched waveguide is practically independent of the etch depth, as long as the vertical waveguide is completely etched through. After etching, a standard wafer rinse process was applied, followed by a PECVD deposition of a silicon nitride (SiN) insulating layer. As the next process step, the p-contacts were formed by selectively removing the SiN on top of the active ridge waveguides and depositing a Ti-Pt-Au layer. After thinning the GaAs wafer to a thickness of $130 \mu\text{m}$, the n-contacts were formed by depositing a Ni-Au-Ge on the backside of the entire wafer.

Figure 4 presents scanning electron microscope images of various waveguide cross sections and elements, including an Euler U-bend and a mode-size converter. Panels (a) and (b) show only deep-etched waveguides, while (d) contains both deep- and shallow-etched waveguides connected by a spot-size converter. The insets of panel (a) as well as panel (b) demonstrate the smoothness of the waveguide surface realized by the process flow described above. The discontinuity at the taper tip visible in panel (d) is a consequence of the process steps involved. For example, the etch masks of the two etch steps must be precisely aligned, with the mask of the

FIG. 4. Scanning electron microscopy pictures of different waveguide cross sections and elements. (a) depicts a deep-etched Euler U-bend segment. The inset shows a close-up of the bent waveguide. (b) shows the cross section of a deep-etched passive waveguide after the SiN insulation layer was deposited. (c) shows an active-passive interface which was prepared by cleaving through the vertical layer structure. In the passive section the double quantum well (DQW) has been removed before the second growth step. (d) depicts a spot-size converter connecting shallow- and deep-etched waveguides.

second etch step being applied to the topology of the shallow-etched waveguide. In addition, the critical dimensions of the taper tip are close to the resolution limit of the i-lithography used. As a result of these factors, it is difficult to precisely control regions where shallow- and deep-etched structures intersect.

Finally, the wafers were separated into smaller chips (laser bars). Facets of high optical quality were formed by cleaving along crystallographically defined surfaces. The results presented in Sec. IV A were obtained with uncoated facets. In contrast, thin-film coatings were applied to the devices measured in Secs. IV B and IV C to obtain a power reflectivity of 0 % (30 %) and 30 % (0 %) at the front (rear) facets, respectively.

IV. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

A. Waveguide characterization

To determine the internal parameters of laser diodes, such as internal efficiency η_i and absorption coefficient α_a , resonator length dependent measurements of the differential efficiency η_d (or laser threshold I_{th}) can be fitted using analytical expressions.³³

This procedure can also be applied to two-section lasers containing active and passive waveguides. An appropriate expression for the differential efficiency can be derived as:

$$\eta_d = \eta_i \frac{\alpha_m}{\alpha_m + \alpha_a} \frac{(1 - R)T_{ap}e^{-\alpha_p L_p}}{1 - RT_{ap}^2 e^{-2\alpha_p L_p} + T_{ap}e^{-\alpha_p L_p}(1 - R)} \quad (2)$$

Here, two identical power facet reflectivity values R as well as a neglectable parasitic reflection at the active-passive interface have been assumed. A schematic depiction illustrating several of the parameters is shown in the inset of Fig. 5 (a), where T_{ap} , α_a , α_p , L_a and L_p are the transmittance at the active-passive interface, the absorption coefficient of the active section, the absorption coefficient of the passive section, the active section length, and the passive section length, respectively. The mirror losses α_m are given as

$$\alpha_m = -\frac{1}{L - L_p} \ln(R) - \frac{1}{L - L_p} \ln(T_{ap}) + \frac{L_p}{L - L_p} \alpha_p \quad (3)$$

with $L = L_a + L_p$ being the total length of the two-section laser. It is noteworthy that Eqs. 2 and 3 are identical to expressions following from the effective mirror approach presented in Ref. 34.

To characterize the internal parameters of three different waveguide types enabled by this platform suitable test structures have been processed as shown in Fig. 5 (a). The first device (type I) contains a shallow-etched ridge waveguide with active region over its entire length, whereas device types II & III contain a 2 mm long active waveguide section and a 4 mm shallow-/deep-etched passive waveguide, respectively. In the latter device the shallow- and deep-etched section are connected with a spot-size converter as introduced in Sec. II B

Typical results of the power-current characteristics of these Fabry-Pérot lasers are shown in Fig. 5 (b) for

FIG. 5. Waveguide loss characterization of different waveguide types. (a) depicts the three investigated lasers. Here, device type I consists of a single active waveguide section and the device types II & III of a 2 mm long active section (on the left) and two different waveguide types (on the right). While the active sections are shallow-etched in all cases, the passive section is shallow-etched in type II and deep-etched in type III. (b) shows two measured power-current characteristics of each of the three device types with $L = 6$ mm. Note that the red lines of device type III are partially hidden beneath the blue lines of type II. (c) shows the inverse differential efficiency as function of the total resonator length $L = L_a + L_p$. The experimental results are depicted as black error bars. The corresponding mean values are connected by a dotted black line as guide for the eye. These results were fitted using Eqs. 2 and 3 and are depicted as red lines.

TABLE I. Summary of the propagation loss coefficients of the three investigated waveguide types (see Figure 5(b)) obtained by fitting Eqs. 2 and 3 to the experimental data shown in Figure 5(c). The internal efficiency was used as free parameter whereas α_a was fixed to the value obtained for device type I

Device type	I	II	III
η_i (%)	78	73	72
α_a (cm^{-1})	3.60	3.60 (fixed)	3.60 (fixed)
α_p (cm^{-1})	/	0.42	0.51

$L = 6$ mm. These measurements were repeated after successively shortening the resonator length L in 1 mm steps by re-cleaving the laser chips at the front facet. The resonator length dependence of the slope of the measured lasers is shown in Fig. 5 (c) as inverse differential efficiency as function of the total resonator length L (black error bars). The results of device type I have been fitted using the equations introduced above by setting $R = 0.3$, $T_{ap} = 1$ and $L_p = 0$ leading to an internal efficiency of $\eta_i = 0.78$ and an absorption coefficient of $\alpha_a = 3.60 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (-15.6 dB/cm). Adapting L_p the fits of device types II & III resulted in $\alpha_p = 0.42 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (-1.8 dB/cm) and $\alpha_p = 0.51 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (-2.2 dB/cm) for the shallow- and deep-etched passive waveguides, respectively. Here, α_a was

fixed to the value of device type I. All results are summarized in Table I.

B. Ring resonator characterization

To characterize the Euler U-bend based racetrack ring resonator design as introduced in Sec. II test devices have been fabricated, see Fig. 6 (a). These structures feature a 3.5 mm-long shallow-etched active waveguide section that is connected to a passive section containing a directional coupler that connects the ring resonator. This bus waveguide further leads to the front facet using a 3° tilted, 1 mm long out-couple bend.

To get first results, the active region was directly used to generate TE-polarized amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) to probe the TE ring resonances using an on-chip broadband source. The optical spectra were measured by collecting the emitted ASE on the front facet of the chip using an optical spectrum analyzer (Yokogawa AQ6373B). In this experiment the device under test was protected from optical feedback by an optical isolator having an isolation of about 60 dB.

Panel (b) of Fig. 6 shows the measured optical ASE spectrum from 1049.5 nm to 1050.5 nm containing densely spaced power drops caused by the ring res-

onator. The corresponding free spectral range was measured to be 0.095 nm. In addition, it is apparent that no higher order modes get excited. The black dotted line in the left panel of (b) shows a close up of one resonance around 1050 nm. A Lorentzian fit of this resonance is depicted as red line and reveals a spectral width at full width half maximum of $\Delta\lambda = 0.023$ nm and an extinction ratio of 1.8 dB. However, these results are limited by the spectral resolution of the used OSA which is 0.02 nm.

To obtain more accurate results, the ring resonators were additionally characterized using a single frequency DFB laser from TOPTICA EAGLEYARD emitting at 1064 nm (EYP-DFB-1064-00025-1500-BFY12-0002). In these measurements the probe light was coupled into the device under test through the front facet. By sweeping the injection current of the DFB laser from 50 mA to 150 mA its emission wavelength shifts linearly with 2.47 pm/mA, see Fig. 6 (c). The optical signal passing the ring resonator at the through port was detected measuring the photocurrent using the integrated active region as monitor diode (MD). Additionally, a polarization filter was used to probe the TE and TM response separately. More information on this method can be found in Appendix A 2.

The resulting baseline corrected and normalized transmission spectra³⁵ are depicted in Fig. 6 (d). The corresponding free spectral ranges were determined to be 95.6 pm and 92.0 pm for the TE and TM polarized light, respectively. By using the physical resonator length L of 3067 μm the resulting group indices can be estimated to be $n_{g,\text{TE}} = 3.86$ and $n_{g,\text{TM}} = 4.01$.

By fitting the analytical expression of the all-pass ring resonator transmittance

$$T = \frac{t^2 - 2ta \cdot \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}n_gL\right) + a^2}{1 - 2ta \cdot \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}n_gL\right) + (ta)^2} \quad (4)$$

to the measured data shown in panel (d) several resonator characteristics can be assessed.^{36–38} The single pass amplitude transmission a and self-coupling coefficient t determined by the fit give direct access to the loaded quality factor Q_L and intrinsic quality factor Q_I of the resonator using

$$Q_L = \frac{\pi n_g L \sqrt{ta}}{\lambda_0(1 - ta)} \quad (5)$$

and

$$Q_I = \frac{2Q_L}{1 \pm \sqrt{T_0}}. \quad (6)$$

Here, $T_0 = 10^{-\text{ER}/10}$ is the normalized power transmittance at the through port at resonance, with ER being the extinction ratio. The plus and minus signs of the square root correspond to under- and over-coupled resonators, respectively.³⁹

The results obtained by this fitting procedure are summarized in Table II for both polarization modes. The

fact that $t > a$ indicates that the resonator is under-coupled which explains the moderate extinction ratios ER of about 5.4 dB to 7.1 dB. From the a values the averaged absorption coefficients of the ring resonator were calculated to be 0.89 cm^{-1} (-3.9 dB/cm) and 0.74 cm^{-1} (-3.2 dB/cm) for TE and TM modes, respectively. Using the definition $Q_L = \lambda_0/\Delta\lambda$ the spectral widths were determined to be 5.4 pm and 4.6 pm for the TE and TM polarized light, respectively. It is noteworthy to mention that these results were not limited by the measurement method, for more information we refer to Appendix A 2.

C. Ring-resonator-coupled lasers

High-Q ring resonators are of interest for several applications. One of these is their use in the context of integrated laser devices as wavelength selective element.⁴⁰ A simple layout of such a ring-resonator-coupled laser is schematically depicted in Fig. 7 (a). Here, the add-drop ring resonator is realized as in-line optical reflector which provides wavelength-selective feedback at its resonances. The laser cavity is formed between this ring mirror and the front facet which was coated to have 30 % reflectance. The waveguides at the anti-reflection coated rear facet were angled at 3° to the facet normal to avoid parasitic reflections.

Figure 7 (b) shows the power-current-characteristics of this device measured at the front and rear facet where the latter contains the emitted power from both passports. The laser threshold and the slope efficiency at the front facet were determined to be 65 mA and 0.14 W/A. At an injection current of 150 mA a power of 12.5 mW is achieved. The discontinuities of the power-current curve indicate longitudinal mode hops. However, in between these hops the measured emitted spectrum indicates single-mode emission, see Fig. 7 (c). At an injection current of 140 mA the side-mode suppression ratio (SMSR) is higher than 40 dB.

The free spectral range (FSR) of 47 pm visible in the optical spectra corresponds to a resonator roundtrip length of about 6 mm using $\text{FSR} = \frac{\lambda_0^2}{Ln_g}$ and applying the TE-mode group index of $n_{g,\text{TE}} = 3.86$ determined in Sec. IV B. This length, however, neither corresponds to the ring circumference ($L_r = 3067 \mu\text{m}$) nor the physical resonator roundtrip length $L_{\text{pr}} = 2L_a +$

TABLE II. Summary of the ring resonator characteristics obtained by fitting Eq. 4 to the experimental results depicted in Fig. 6 (d) followed by the usage of Eqs. 5 and 6

Polarization	TE	TM
Self-coupling coefficient t	0.960	0.957
Amplitude transmission a	0.873	0.893
Loaded quality factor Q_L	196,797	230,807
Intrinsic quality factor Q_I	255,958	320,545

FIG. 6. Ring resonator characterization. (a) schematically depicts the all-pass ring resonator device used for characterization. (b) shows the transmission spectra of the ring resonator measured using the active section as amplified spontaneous emission source, while the right panel depicts a close up of a single resonance around 1050 nm (black line) and a Lorentzian fit (red line). (c) shows the emission spectra of the DFB probe laser used to resolve the ring resonances more precisely. The inset shows the peak wavelength shift λ_{rel} relative to 1064 nm as function of the laser injection current I . (d) depicts the TE and TM resolved resonances as function of the wavelength relative to 1064 nm obtained by exciting the ring resonator through the front facet using the DFB laser and measuring the photocurrent at the active device section located at the rear facet. The red lines represent fits of the experimental data using Eq. 4

$2L_{\text{pr}} + 0.5L_{\text{r}} = 10\,064\,\mu\text{m}$, where $L_{\text{a}} = 2250\,\mu\text{m}$ and $L_{\text{pr}} = 2015\,\mu\text{m}$ are the gain section and passive waveguide routing lengths, respectively. Rather, the emission wavelength is defined by the ring-resonator-coupled cavity FSR described by the optical vernier effect.^{26,41} This hypothesis is supported by intracavity reflectometry measurements. For this purpose, a high-resolution spectrum below laser threshold ($I = 60\,\text{mA}$) was measured with a double echelle monochromator (LTB DEMON), see Fig. 7 (e). The corresponding resonator lengths can be determined using a Fourier transform based analysis, see Appendix A 3 for more information. The results of this procedure are shown in Fig. 7 (f) and show a dominant contribution from the coupled cavity (vernier cavity) and a minor effect from the physical cavity length marked by L_{ver} and L_{res} , respectively.

Based on the waveguide and ring resonator figures of merit determined in Secs. IV A and IV B and summarized in Table I and II the effective reflectivity R_{eff} of the in-line ring resonator mirror can be calculated following the approach presented in Ref. 26. The resulting power reflectivity $|R_{\text{eff}}|^2$ is shown in Fig. 7 (d) having a peak value of 14%. The impact of this ring mirror on the laser linewidth $\Delta\nu = \Delta\nu_{\text{FP}}/F^2$ is described by the chirp reduction factor F .^{26,42} Here, $\Delta\nu_{\text{FP}}$ is the intrinsic linewidth of the Fabry-Pérot gain section using 30% and $|R_{\text{eff}}|^2$ as the front facet and ring mirror reflectivities. The calculated F as shown in Fig. 7 (d) has a value of

3.8 at resonance indicating a possible linewidth reduction of factor 14.4.

V. DISCUSSION

The results of the waveguide loss characterization presented in Sec. IV A lead to absorption coefficients of $3.60\,\text{cm}^{-1}$ and $0.42\,\text{cm}^{-1}$ (1.82 dB/cm) for the 2.5 μm wide single-mode shallow-etched active and passive waveguides, respectively. The results from other active/passive GaAs-based waveguide platforms having a similar emission wavelength (1030 nm and 1064 nm) and ridge width (3 μm and 4 μm) show with $\alpha_{\text{a}} = 3.44\,\text{cm}^{-1}$ similar losses for the active waveguide¹² but with $\alpha_{\text{p}} = 0.6\,\text{cm}^{-1}$ and $\alpha_{\text{p}} = 4.05\,\text{cm}^{-1}$ higher losses for the passive waveguide.^{9,12} In addition, the losses of the deep-etched passive waveguides of our platform have been measured to be $0.51\,\text{cm}^{-1}$ (2.21 dB/cm), only 21% higher than those of the shallow one.

The passive waveguide losses achieved in this work are comparable to those reported for commercially available InP-PICs, which range from 2 dB/cm to 4 dB/cm.^{21,22,43} In comparison, the losses of open-access silicon-on-insulator (SOI) based waveguide platforms are in the order of 1 dB/cm to 2 dB/cm.^{23,44} It should be noted that most SOI platforms combine both, a high index contrast and single-mode waveguides. In the case of

FIG. 7. Ring-resonator-coupled laser characterization. (a) shows a schematic representation of the laser design, which consists of a 2.25 mm long gain section connected to an in-line ring resonator mirror. Note that the illustration is not to scale. (b) displays the power-current characteristics obtained from the front and rear facets. (c) shows measured optical spectra obtained at 80 mA and 140 mA. (d) depicts the power reflectivity and the chirp reduction factor calculated using the parameters obtained in Sec. IV B and summarized in Table II. (e) and (f) show a spectrum measured below the laser threshold using a double echelle monochromator, and the resulting Fourier transform-based intracavity reflectogram.

the proposed GaAs-PIC platform, single-mode shallow-etched and multi-mode deep-etched must be combined to achieve this. Recently, multi-mode SOI waveguides have been shown to achieve very low losses in the order of 0.1 dB/cm.⁴⁵ However, it is to note that the mentioned loss figures were obtained for wavelengths around 1550 nm. Assuming a scattering loss dependence of $\propto \lambda^{-3}$ as suggested by the normalized Payne-Lacey model,⁴⁶ waveguides at 1050 nm are about 3.2 times more susceptible to scattering losses than those at C-band wavelengths.

In Sec. IV B results of the ring resonator characterization were presented. The intrinsic quality factors were measured to be $2.6 \cdot 10^5$ and $3.2 \cdot 10^5$ for TE and TM polarized light, respectively. These values exceed the Q-factors achieved for micro-ring resonators fabricated on various InP platforms.^{47–50} In comparison, Q-factors above 10^6 have been reported for an all-passive AlGaAs-on-insulator waveguide platform at C-band wavelengths.⁵¹ In the same wavelength range, a thick SOI platform, using a resonator design very similar to the one used in this work, has yielded Q factors exceeding ten million.³⁰ Furthermore, $Q > 10^6$ has recently been reported using a commercially available low-loss SiN waveguide platform, but at a much shorter wavelength of 630 nm.³⁸

The propagation losses of the presented platform extracted from the resonator characterization are 3.63 dB/cm (TE) and 3.20 dB/cm (TM). By assuming TE polarization, negligible insertion losses of the spot-size converters within the resonator and using the losses measured for the straight waveguides the additional distributed losses caused by the bends are 1.68 dB/cm. The upper limit for the insertion losses of the investigated Euler U-bends with $R_{\text{eff}} = 75 \mu\text{m}$ can therefore be estimated to be 0.13 dB. This value is significantly lower than the insertion losses of 0.9 dB reported in Ref. 18 for an Euler U-bend with $R_{\text{eff}} = 114.5 \mu\text{m}$ at $\lambda = 1.3 \mu\text{m}$ and are on par with typical values for InP-based generic foundry platforms.⁴³ In conclusion, the presented results indicate that the achieved Q-factors are limited by losses caused by the waveguide elements within the resonator (U-bends and spot-size converters). A possible reason for losses caused by the spot-size converters is the discontinuity at the taper tip, as shown in Fig. 4 (d). In order to resolve this issue, a further optimization of the process technology appears to be necessary.

The laser results presented in Sec. IV C have demonstrated the ability of the presented GaAs-PIC platform to implement fully integrated ring-resonator-coupled lasers. It reaches 14 mW single sided power emission at 150 mA

which is on par with state-of-the-art heterogeneously integrated ring-based lasers.^{26,52,53} Higher powers could be achieved by increasing the reflection of the in-line ring reflector by transitioning from under- to over-coupled ring resonators by increasing the bus waveguide to ring cross-coupling. The discontinuities in the power-current characteristics indicate unwanted mode hops. Although high SMSR values of above 40 dB were obtained at a current of 140 mA future designs need additional wavelength selective elements. Lasers based on multiple, slightly detuned coupled ring resonators are capable of realizing narrow linewidth emission and can be tuned over a wide wavelength range.^{26,52,54}

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper we presented a GaAs-based PIC platform which supports low-loss passive waveguides as well as monolithically integrated optical gain sections achieved via selective quantum well removal and two-step epitaxy. In addition to standard shallow-etched waveguides, the platform also supports deep-etched ones, enabling the realization of compact curved waveguides.

The losses of the passive waveguides have been determined to be 1.8 dB/cm and 2.2 dB/cm for the shallow- and deep-etched passive variants, respectively, based on cavity length dependent laser measurements. These values are at the same level as those of commercially available InP-PIC platforms. To demonstrate the performance of the GaAs-PIC platform, we realized racetrack ring resonators. These resonators are formed using deep-etched Euler U-bends which are connected to a shallow-etched coupler section via intra-cavity spot-size converters. The characterization revealed high intrinsic optical quality factors of $2.6 \cdot 10^5$ and $3.2 \cdot 10^5$ for TE and TM polarized light.

To demonstrate the use of ring resonators in the context of monolithic GaAs-based laser sources, a ring-resonator-coupled laser was fabricated and characterized. The front facet power was measured to be 14 mW at an injection current of 150 mA. Furthermore, single-mode operation was achieved with up to 40 dB side mode suppression. However, to fully assess the impact of the ring resonator on the laser linewidth, laser frequency noise measurements are required.

The presented results pave the way to the realization of monolithic integration of GaAs-based narrow linewidth and widely-tunable lasers based on coupled ring resonators. To achieve this, the insertion loss of the waveguide elements inside the ring should be further reduced. This might be achieved by increasing the effective radius of the Euler U-bends. Nevertheless, the PIC platform presented here opens the possibility of higher integration densities and more on-chip functionalities than ever before on a GaAs-laser platform.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work presented here was primarily supported by internal funding. We are indebted to Dr. Günther Tränkle for this opportunity. In addition, this work was practically supported by the Research Fab Germany (FMD) under grant no. 16FMDQ2.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Appendix A: Methods

1. Simulations

The modal profiles shown in Fig. 2 were calculated using the commercial software FIMMWAVE from Photon Design⁵⁵. The quasi-TE solver used is based on the finite difference method and a constant spatial grid of $\Delta x = 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ and $\Delta y = 0.02 \mu\text{m}$ was used. The modal transmittance data presented in Sec. II were obtained using the FIMMPROP module based on the mode expansion method. Here, 60 quasi-TE modes were considered. The taper algorithm used to evaluate longitudinally non-uniform waveguide segments (spot-size converters and U-bends) was set to its default settings (integrationOrder: 0, Tolerance: 0.01, minStepsizeFrac: 0.01). All simulations have been performed at a wavelength of 1064 nm.

2. DFB-laser based ring resonator characterization

Since the processed ring resonators have a spectral width on the order of or below the resolution of most optical spectrum analyzers, they cannot be used to directly measure the all-pass ring resonator filtered spectra. Alternatively, we measured the ring resonances by scanning the emitted wavelength of an external probe laser whose peak wavelength shift was previously characterized to be 2.27 pm/mA, see Figure 6 (c), similar to what was done in ref.⁵⁶.

The emission wavelength of the DFB laser used (TOPTICA EAGLEYARD, EYP-DFB-1064-00025-1500-BFY12-0002) was changed from 1064.01 nm to 1064.25 nm by varying its injection current from 50 mA to 150 mA in 0.1 mA steps. This leads to a wavelength resolution of 0.25 pm. Before coupling into the front facet of the device under test, the probe light was polarization controlled to distinguish between TE and TM polarization. The active region behind the resonator was used as a monitor diode, where the resulting photocurrent was measured using a Keithley 486 Picoammeter.

The measured ring-resonator-filtered signal was baseline corrected using the asymmetric least squares smoothing method³⁵.

In general, the resulting data is the convolution of the measured ring resonances and the spectral line shape of the DFB laser used. However, since the linewidth of the used laser of 2 MHz is about 600 times narrower than the measured ring resonances with 1.2 GHz, its shape can be assumed to be delta-like.

3. Intracavity reflectometry

Reflectometry is a well-known method for the investigation of diode lasers and integrated waveguide devices^{57,58}. Here, an adaptation of these methods is described that was used to obtain the results shown in Fig. 7 (f). First, the measured optical spectrum OS is interpolated to be equidistant in frequency f space. Next, the optical spectrum is Fourier transformed using $FFT(OS(f))$. Finally, the $FFT(OS(f))$ is plotted against the spatial grid Z defined from $0\ \mu\text{m}$ to $N \cdot \Delta z$ in steps of $\Delta z = \frac{c_0 \Delta t}{n_g}$, where Δz is the spatial resolution, $\Delta t = \frac{1}{N \Delta f}$ is the temporal resolution, and N is the number of discrete entries of $OS(f)$. It can be seen that the spatial grid depends on the group index n_g . Therefore, TE and TM spectral data must be scaled using $n_{g,TE}$ and $n_{g,TM}$, respectively.

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PLEASE CITE THIS ARTICLE AS DOI: 10.1063/5.0223134

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